

World News of Natural Sciences

An International Scientific Journal

WNOFNS 36 (2021) 9-41

EISSN 2543-5426

World Inventory of Beetles of the Family *Bostrichidae* (Coleoptera). Part 2. Check List from 1758 to 2007

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ABSTRACT

This paper presents list of beetles of the family Bostrichidae and their occurrence. The paper includes: 2 subfamilies, 5 tribes, 60 genera, 2 subgenera and 409 species of beetles belonging to the family Bostrichidae.

Keywords: *Apatinae, Bostrichinae, Apatini, Dinapatini, Bostrichini, Sinoxylonini, Xyloperthini*

Subfamilies

<i>Apatinae</i>10
<i>Bostrichinae</i>13

– Check List –

Kingdom *Animalia*

Phylum *Arthropoda*

Class *Hexapoda*

Order *Coleoptera*

Family *Bostrichidae* Latreille, 1802

Subfamily *Apatinae* Jacquelin du Val, 1861

Tribe *Apatini* Jacquelin du Val, 1861

Genus *Apate* Fabricius 1775

Apate bicolor Fahraeus, 1871
Distribution: South Africa

Apate bilabiata Lesne, 1909
Distribution: East Africa

Apate cephalotes (Olivier, 1790)
Distribution: East and South Africa, Madagascar, Comoros, Mauritius, Reunion

Apate degener Murray, 1867
Distribution: West and East Africa, Zanzibar

Apate ecomata Lesne, 1929
Distribution: Somalia

Apate geayi Lesne, 1907
Distribution: Madagascar

Apate indistincta Murray, 1867
Distribution: East and South Africa, Mauritius

Apate lignicolor Fairmaire, 1883
Distribution: Africa, Madagascar

Apate monachus Fabricius, 1775

Distribution: Africa, South Europe, Arabian Peninsula, Comoros (introduced), Central America (introduced)

Apate raricoma Lesne, 1924

Distribution: West Africa

Apate reflexa Lesne, 1909

Distribution: West Africa

Apate scoparia Lesne 1909

Distribution: East Africa

Apate subcalva Lesne, 1923

Distribution: West Africa

Apate submedia Walker 1858

Distribution: South India, Sri Lanka

Apate terebrans (Pallas, 1772)

Distribution: Africa, Arabian Peninsula, South and Central America (introduced)

Genus *Phonapate* Lesne, 1895

Phonapate andriana Lesne, 1909

Distribution: Madagascar

Phonapate chan (Semenow, 1891)

Distribution: Kazakhstan, Turkmenistan, Uzbekistan

Phonapate densoana Lesne, 1934

Distribution: Madagascar

Phonapate deserti (Semenow, 1891)

Distribution: Kazakhstan, Uzbekistan, Turkmenistan

Phonapate discreta Lesne, 1906

Distribution: Island of Principe

Phonapate fimbriata Lesne, 1909

Distribution: India, South China, Vietnam. Indonesia (Celebes)

Phonapate madecassa Lesne, 1899

Distribution: Madagascar

Phonapate nitidipennis (Waterouse, 1881)

Distribution: South Europe (Cyprus), Africa, Arabian Peninsula, Iraq, Iran, Afghanistan
Pakistan

Phonapate porrecta Lesne, 1900

Distribution: East and West Africa, Zanzibar

Phonapate stridula Lesne 1909

Distribution: India, Burma, Vietnam

Phonapate sublobata Lesne, 1909

Distribution: Indonesia (Sumatra)

Genus ***Xylomedes*** Lesne, 1902

Xylomedes carbonnieri (Lesne, 1897)

Distribution: Algeria, Tunisia, Libya

Xylomedes cornifrons (Baudi di Selve, 1873)

Distribution: Cyprus, Israel, Lebanon, South Turkey, Syria

Xylomedes coronata (Marseul, 1883)

Distribution: North Africa

Xylomedes laticornis (Lesne, 1895)

Distribution: Egypt, Yemen, Abyssinia, Eritrea

Xylomedes rufocoronata (Fairmaire, 1892)

Distribution: North and North-East Africa, Arabian Peninsula

Xylomedes scutifrons Lesne, 1908

Distribution: South-West Africa

Xylomedes turcica Lesne, 1941

Distribution: South Turkey, Syria, Iraq

Tribe ***Dinapatini*** Lesne, 1909

Genus ***Dinapate*** Horn, 1886

Dinapate hughleechi Cooper, 1986

Distribution: Mexico

Dinapate wrightii Horn, 1886

Distribution: USA (California, Colorado)

Subfamily *Bostrichinae* Latreille, 1802

Tribe *Bostrichini* Latreille, 1802

Genus *Amphicerus* LeConte 1861

Subgenus *Amphicerus*

Amphicerus (Amphicerus) clunalis Lesne, 1939

Distribution: Mexico

Amphicerus (Amphicerus) cornutus (Pallas, 1772)

Distribution: South-West USA, Central and South America, Antilles, Fiji (introduced), Hawaii (introduced), Europe (Poland) (introduced)

Amphicerus (Amphicerus) galapaganus Lesne, 1910

Distribution: Galapagos Islands

Amphicerus (Amphicerus) hamatus (Fabricius, 1787)

Distribution: Canada, USA, Mexico, Cuba, Europe (introduced)

Amphicerus (Amphicerus) lignator (Lesne, 1899)

Distribution: Venezuela, Colombia

Amphicerus (Amphicerus) securimentum Lesne, 1939

Distribution: Mexico

Amphicerus (Amphicerus) tubularis (Gorham, 1883)

Distribution: Mexico, Panama

Subgenus *Caenophrada* Waterhouse, 1888

Amphicerus (Caenophrada) anobioides (Waterhouse, 1888)

Distribution: India, Burma, Sri Lanka, Arabian Peninsula, Abyssinia, Eritrea

Amphicerus (Caenophrada) bimaculatus (Olivier, 1790)

Distribution: South Europe, North Africa, Asia Minor, Middle East, Caucasus, Turkmenistan, USA (introduced)

Amphicerus (Caenophrada) caenophradoides (Lesne, 1895)

Distribution: Vietnam, Cambodia, Indonesia (Sumatra)

Amphicerus (Caenophrada) malayanus (Lesne, 1898)

Distribution: Indonesia (Sumatra, Kalimantan), Malaysia (Malay Peninsula)

Amphicerus (Caenophrada) simplex (Horn 1885)
Distribution: USA (Texas, Arizona, New Mexico)

Amphicerus (Caenophrada) teres Horn 1878
Distribution: USA (California, Texas, Arizona)

Genus ***Apatides*** Casey, 1898

Apatides fortis (LeConte, 1866)
Distribution: South-West USA, Mexico, Costa Rica, Nicaragua, Columbia

Genus ***Bostrichus*** Geoffroy, 1762

Bostrichus capucinus (Linnaeus, 1758)
Distribution: Europe, North Africa, Asia Minor, Middle East, Altai, USA (introduced)

Genus ***Bostrycharis*** Lesne, 1925

Bostrycharis niveosquamosus Lesne, 1925
Distribution: South-East Africa

Genus ***Bostrychoplites*** Lesne, 1899

Bostrychoplites arabicus Lesne, 1934
Distribution: Yemen

Bostrychoplites armatus Lesne 1899
Distribution: East Africa, Madagascar, Mauritius

Bostrychoplites cornutus (Olivier, 1790)
Distribution: Africa South of Sahara, Yemen, Madagascar, Comoros, Reunion, Mauritius, USA (introduced), Europe (introduced)

Bostrychoplites cylindricus (Fahraeus, 1871)
Distribution: Africa South of Sahara

Bostrychoplites dicerus Lesne, 1899
Distribution: West Africa

Bostrychoplites guineanus Lesne, 1923
Distribution: West Africa

Bostrychoplites luniger (J. Thomson, 1858)

Distribution: West Africa

Bostrychoplites megaceros Lesne, 1899

Distribution: East Africa

Bostrychoplites normandi (Lesne, 1897)

Distribution: Africa, Arabian Peninsula, Turkey

Bostrychoplites peltatus Lesne, 1899

Distribution: South Africa, Madagascar (introduced)

Bostrychoplites productus (Imhoff, 1843)

Distribution: West Africa

Bostrychoplites suturalis Lesne, 1931

Distribution: East and South Africa

Bostrychoplites valens Lesne, 1899

Distribution: East Africa

Bostrychoplites vernicatus Lesne, 1923

Distribution: West Africa

Bostrychoplites zickeli (Marseul, 1867)

Distribution: North and North-East Africa, Yemen, Europe (Germany) (introduced)

Genus ***Calophorus*** Lesne, 1906

Calophorus coriaceus Lesne, 1906

Distribution: Australia

Calophorus sinoxylura Lesne, 1937

Distribution: Australia

Genus ***Dexicrates*** Lesne, 1899

Dexicrates robustus (Blanchard, 1851)

Distribution: Argentina, Chile

Genus ***Dolichobostrychus*** Lesne, 1899

Dolichobostrychus angustus (Steinheil, 1872)

Distribution: Brazil, Colombia, Argentina

Dolichobostrychus fossulatus (Blanchard, 1843)

Distribution: Argentina

Dolichobostrychus gracilis (Lesne, 1899)

Distribution: Brazil

Dolichobostrychus granulifrons (Lesne, 1895)

Distribution: Brazil

Dolichobostrychus yunnanus Lesne, 1913

Distribution: China (Yunnan, Sichuan)

Genus ***Dominikia*** Borowski & Wegrzynowicz, 2007

Dominikia bengalensis (Lesne, 1895)

Distribution: India

Dominikia bozasi (Lesne, 1913)

Distribution: Somalia

Dominikia confossa (Fairmaire, 1880)

Distribution: Madagascar

Domnikia crinita (Lesne, 1935)

Distribution: West Africa

Dominikia cristaticeps (Lesne, 1906)

Distribution: Yemen (Socotra)

Dominikia delkeskampi (Vrydagh, 1959)

Distribution: East Africa

Dominikia freyi (Vrydagh, 1959)

Distribution: Brazil, Paraguay

Dominikia ganglbaueri (Lesne, 1899)

Distribution: Brazil

Dominikia jesuita (Fabricius, 1775)

Distribution: Australia, Tasmania, Europe (Germany) (introduced)

Dominikia laminifer (Lesne, 1895)

Distribution: Brazil, Ecuador, Bolivia, Paraguay, Argentina

Dominikia optata (Lesne, 1938)

Distribution: Abyssinia

Dominikia parallela (Lesne, 1895)

Distribution: India, Vietnam, Cambodia, Laos, Taiwan, Philippines, Indonesia (Kalimantan, Sumatra, Java, Sumbava, Flores, Celebes), Australia, USA (introduced), Europe (Austria, Germany) (introduced)

Dominikia peruana Borowski & Wegrzynowicz, 2007

Distribution: Peru, Uruguay

Dominikia reichei (Marseul, 1867)

Distribution: Algeria, Tunisia, Libya, Egypt, Abyssinia, Senegal

Dominikia roonwali (Rai, 1966)

Distribution: India (Uttar Pradesh)

Dominikia rostrifrons (Lesne, 1923)

Distribution: West Africa

Dominikia scopula (Lesne, 1923)

Distribution: East Africa

Dominikia tabori (Reichardt, 1962)

Distribution: Brazil

Dominikia tetraodon (Fairmaire, 1883)

Distribution: Egypt, Abyssinia, Eritrea, Sudan, USA (introduced)

Dominikia tonsa (Imhoff, 1843)

Distribution: Africa South of Sahara, Brazil (introduced)

Dominikia trimorpha (Lesne, 1899)

Distribution: Venezuela, Colombia, Bolivia, Brazil

Dominikia uncinata (Germar, 1824)

Distribution: French Guiana, Colombia, Venezuela, Brazil, Peru, Bolivia, Paraguay, Uruguay, Argentina

Domnikia valida (Lesne, 1899)

Distribution: Brazil, British Guiana, Europe (Germany) (introduced)

Dominikia villosula (Lesne, 1905)

Distribution: East Africa, Reunion

Genus *Heterobostrychus* Lesne, 1899

Heterobostrychus aequalis (Waterhouse, 1884)

Distribution: Madagascar, Comoros, India, China, Laos, Taiwan, Philippines, Indonesia, New guinea, New Caledonia, Australia, New Zealand (introduced), USA (introduced), Europe(introduced), Africa (introduced)

Heterobostrychus ambigenus Lesne, 1920

Distribution: China

Heterobostrychus brunneus (Murray, 1867)

Distribution: Africa, South of Sahara, Madagascar, New Zealand (introduced), USA (introduced), Europe (introduced)

Heterobostrychus hamatipennis (Lesne, 1895)

Distribution: Madagascar, Mauritius, Comoros, India, Sri Lanka, Indonesia, Philippines, China, Taiwan, Vietnam, Laos, Japan, USA (introduced), Europe (Germany) (introduced)

Heterobostrychus pileatus Lesne, 1899

Distribution: India, Thailand, Philippines, Vietnam .Cambodia

Heterobostrychus unicornis Waterhouse, 1879

Distribution: Mozambique, Madagascar, Comoros, India, Burma, Vietnam

Genus *Lichenophanes* Lesne, 1899

Lichennophanes albicans Lesne, 1899

Distribution: Brazil, Argentina

Lichenophanes angustus Casey, 1898

Distribution: Canada, USA

Lichenophanes arizonicus Fisher, 1950

Distribution: USA (Arizona)

Lichenophanes armiger (LeConte, 1866)

Distribution: Canada, USA

Lichenophanes bechyneorum Vrydagh, 1959

Distribution: Argentina

Lichenophanes bedeli (Lesne, 1895)

Distribution: Colombia, Brazil

Lichenophanes bicornis (Weber, 1801)

Distribution: Canada. USA

Lichenophanes californicus (Horn, 1878)

Distribution: USA (California)

Lichenophanes carinipennis (Lewis, 1896)

Distribution: Sri Lanka, Andamans, Taiwan, Cambodia, Japan

Lichenophanes caudatus (Lesne, 1895)

Distribution: Gabon, Cameroon, Guinea Bissau, „Old Calabar”

Lichenophanes collarti (Vrydagh, 1959)

Distribution: East Africa

Lichenophanes corticeus Lesne, 1908

Distribution: East Africa

Lichenophanes egenus Lesne, 1923

Distribution: West Africa

Lichenophanes egregius Lesne, 1934

Distribution: Peru

Lichenophanes fasciatus (Lesne, 1895)

Distribution: Brazil, Colombia

Lichenophanes fascicularis (Fahraeus, 1871)

Distribution: Africa South of Sahara, Comoros

Lichenophanes fasciculatus (Fall, 1909)

Distribution: USA (California)

Lichenophanes funebris Lesne, 1938

Distribution: South Africa

Lichenophanes indutus Lesne, 1935

Distribution: West Africa

Lichenophanes iniquus (Lesne, 1895)

Distribution: Sierra Leone, Burkina Faso, Togo

Lichenophanes insignitus (Fairmaire, 1883)

Distribution, Abyssinia

Lichenophanes katanganus Lesne, 1935

Distribution: West Africa

Lichenophanes kunckeli Lesne, 1895

Distribution: Madagascar

Lichenophanes marmoratus Lesne, 1899

Distribution: West Africa

Lichenophanes martini Lesne, 1899

Distribution: Madagascar

Lichenophanes morbillosus (Quedenfeldt, 1887)

Distribution: West Africa

Lichenophanes numida Lesne, 1899

Distribution: Europe (South Iberian Peninsula, Sardinia), North Africa

Lichenophanes oberthuri Lesne, 1899

Distribution: West Africa

Lichenophanes penicillatus (Lesne, 1895)

Distribution: Mexico

Lichenophanes percristatus Lesne, 1924

Distribution: West Africa

Lichenophanes perrieri Lesne, 1899

Distribution: Madagascar

Lichenophanes plicatus (Guerin-Meneville, 1844)

Distribution: Guatemala, French Guiana, Colombia, Venezuela, Brazil, Paraguay

Lichenophanes rutilans Reichardt, 1970

Distribution: Ecuador (Galapagos Islands)

Lichenophanes spectabilis (Lesne, 1895)

Distribution: USA (California), Mexico

Lichenophanes tristis (Fahraeus, 1871)

Distribution: South Africa

Lichenophanes truncaticollis (LeConte, 1866)

Distribution: Canada, USA

Lichenophanes tuberosus Lesne, 1934

Distribution: Mexico

Lichenophanes varius (Illiger, 1801)

Distribution: Europe, Caucasus, Middle East, North Africa

Lichenophanes verrucosus (Gorham, 1883)

Distribution: Guatemala, Costa Rica

Lichenophanes weissii Lesne, 1908

Distribution: Zaire

Lichenophanes zanzibaricus Lesne, 1925

Distribution: Tanzania (Zanzibar)

Genus *Megabostrichus* Chujo 1964

Megabostrichus imadatei Chujo, 1964

Distribution: Thailand

Genus *Micrapate* Casey, 1898

Micrapate albertiana Lesne, 1943

Distribution: West and East Africa

Micrapate amplicollis (Lesne, 1899)

Distribution: Paraguay

Micrapate atra (Lesne, 1899)

Distribution, Brazil

Micrapate bicostula Lesne, 1906

Distribution: Brazil

Micrapate bilobata Fisher, 1950

Distribution: USA (Texas)

Micrapate brasiliensis (Lesne, 1899)

Distribution: Brazil, USA (introduced)

Micrapate brevipes (Lesne, 1899)

Distribution: Brazil

Micrapate bruchi Lesne, 1931

Distribution: Argentina

Micrapate brunripes (Fabricius, 1801)

Distribution: Colombia, Venezuela, Brazil, Mexico, Antilles, Europe (introduced)

Micrapate catamarcana Lesne, 1931

Distribution: Argentina

Micrapate cordobiana Lesne, 1931

Distribution: Argentina

Micrapate cribripennis (Lesne, 1899)

Distribution: Brazil

Micrapate cristicauda Casey, 1898

Distribution: USA (Florida, Maryland, Virginia, District of Columbia)

Micrapate dinoderoides (Horn, 1878)

Distribution: USA (Arizona, Texas)

Micrapate discrepans Lesne, 1939

Distribution: Guatemala

Micrapate exigua (Lesne, 1899)

Distribution: Colombia

Micrapate foraminata Lesne, 1906

Distribution: Panama, Costa Rica

Micrapate fusca (Lesne, 1899)

Distribution: Central America, Cuba

Micrapate germaini (Lesne, 1899)

Distribution: Brazil, Paraguay

Micrapate guatemalensis Lesne, 1906

Distribution: Guatemala, Mexico

Micrapate horni (Lesne, 1899)

Distribution: Brazil

Micrapate humeralis (Blanchard, 1851)

Distribution: Chile

Micrapate kiangana Lesne, 1935

Distribution: East Africa

Micrapate labialis Lesne, 1906

Distribution: Guatemala, Mexico, USA (introduced)

Micrapate leechi Vrydagh, 1960

Distribution: USA (California)

Micrapate mexicana Fisher, 1950

Distribution: Mexico, USA (introduced)

Micrapate neglecta Lesne, 1906

Distribution: Sierra Leone

Micrapate obesa (Lesne 1899)

Distribution: Brazil

Micrapate pinguis Lesne, 1939

Distribution: Mexico

Micrapate puberula Lesne, 1906

Distribution: Tchad

Micrapate pupulus Lesne, 1906

Distribution: Amazonian forests

Micrapate quadraticollis (Lesne, 1899)

Distribution: French Guiana

Micrapate scabrata (Erichson, 1847)

Distribution: Panama, Colombia, Ecuador, Peru, Bolivia, Chile, USA (introduced)

Micrapate scapularis (Gorham, 1883)

Distribution: Guatemala, Mexico

Micrapate schoutedeni Lesne, 1935

Distribution: Central and East Africa

Micrapate sericeicollis Lesne, 1906

Distribution: Guatemala, Mexico

Micrapate simplicipennis (Lesne, 1895)

Distribution: India, Burma, Vietnam

Micrapate straeleni Vrydagh, 1954

Distribution: Zaire, Mozambique

Micrapate unguiculata Lesne, 1906

Distribution: Mexico

Micrapate wagneri Lesne, 1906

Distribution: Brazil, Argentina

Micrapate xyloperthoides (Jacquelin do Val, 1859)

Distribution: France, Italy (Sicily), Spain, North Africa, USA (introduced)

Genus ***Neoterius*** Lesne, 1899

Neoterius fairmairei (Lesne, 1895)

Distribution: Mexico, Peru, Chile

Neoterius mystax (Blanchard, 1851)

Distribution: Brazil, Peru, Chile

Neoterius pulvinatus (Blanchard, 1851)

Distribution: Brazil, Chile

Genus *Parabostrychus* Lesne, 1899

Parabostrychus acuticollis Lesne, 1913

Distribution: India, Nepal, Southern China, Taiwan

Parabostrychus elongatus (Lesne, 1895)

Distribution: Vietnam

Genus *Sinoxylodes* Lesne, 1899

Sinoxylodes curtulus (Erichson, 1847)

Distribution: Guatemala, Brazil, Peru, Argentina

Tribe *Sinoxylonini* Lesne, 1899

Genus *Calodectes* Lesne, 1906

Calodectes laniger Lesne, 1906

Distribution: South Africa

Genus *Calodrypta* Lesne, 1906

Calodrypta exarmata Lesne, 1906

Distribution: East and South Africa, Zanzibar

Genus *Calopertha* Lesne, 1906

Calopertha costatipennis Lesne, 1906

Distribution: North-East Africa, Yemen

Calopertha kalaharensis Lesne, 1906

Distribution: Namibia

Calopertha subretusa (Ancey, 1881)

Distribution: North, East and West Africa, Arabian Peninsula, India

Calopertha truncatula (Ancey, 1881)

Distribution: Saharian Region, Somalia, Arabian Peninsula, Iran, Penjab

Genus ***Sinocalon*** Lesne 1906

Sinocalon pilosulum Lesne, 1906

Distribution: Argentina

Sinocalon reticulatum Lesne, 1906

Distribution: Argentina

Sinocalon vestitum (Lesne, 1895)

Distribution: Bolivia, Argentina

Genus ***Sinoxylon*** Duftschmid, 1825

Sinoxylon anale Lesne, 1897

Distribution: Cosmopolitan

Sinoxylon angolense Lesne, 1906

Distribution: West Africa

Sinoxylon atratum Lesne, 1897

Distribution: India

Sinoxylon beelsoni Lesne, 1931

Distribution: Burma

Sinoxylon bellicosum Lesne, 1906

Distribution: South Africa

Sinoxylon birmanum Lesne, 1906

Distribution: Burma, Europe (Germany) (introduced)

Sinoxylon brazzai Lesne, 1895

Distribution: West Africa

Sinoxylon bufo Lesne, 1906

Distribution: Indonesia (Java, Borneo)

Sinoxylon cafrum Lesne, 1905

Distribution: South and West Africa

Sinoxylon capillatum Lesne, 1895

Distribution: Kashmir

Sinoxylon ceratoniae (Linnaeus, 1758)

Distribution: Africa, Arabian Peninsula, Iraq, Europe (introduced)

Sinoxylon circuitum Lesne, 1897

Distribution: India

Sinoxylon crassum Lesne, 1897

Distribution: India, Burma, Himalayas, Cambodia, Laos, Vietnam, Thailand, Malaysia, Philippines, Europe (Germany, Poland) (introduced)

Sinoxylon cucumella Lesne, 1906

Distribution: Bhutan, Vietnam

Sinoxylon cuneolus Lesne, 1906

Distribution: South Africa

Sinoxylon dichroum Lesne, 1906

Distribution: Burma, Northern India

Sinoxylon divaricatum Lesne, 1906

Distribution: Somalia

Sinoxylon doliolum Lesne, 1905

Distribution: East Africa

Sinoxylon epipleurale Lesne, 1906

Distribution: East Africa

Sinoxylon erasicauda Lesne, 1906

Distribution: East Africa

Sinoxylon eucerum Lesne, 1932

Distribution: China

Sinoxylon flabrarius Lesne 1906

Distribution: India, Bhutan, South China, Vietnam, Europe (introduced)

Sinoxylon fuscovestitum Lesne, 1919

Distribution: Laos

Sinoxylon indicum Lesne, 1897

Distribution: India, Burma

Sinoxylon japonicum Lesne, 1895

Distribution: Japan, China, USA (introduced)

Sinoxylon lesnei Vrydagh, 1955

Distribution: Togo, Guinea Bissau

Sinoxylon luzonicum Lesne, 1932

Distribution: Philippines

Sinoxylon lycturum Lesne, 1936

Distribution: Burma

Sinoxylon malaccanum Lesne, 1930

Distribution: Malaysia

Sinoxylon mangiferae Chujo, 1936

Distribution: Taiwan

Sinoxylon marseuli Lesne, 1895

Distribution: India, Vietnam, Indonesia

Sinoxylon muricatum (Linnaeus, 1767)

Distribution Southern Europe, Caucasus, Asia Minor, North Africa, Middle East, USA (introduced)

Sinoxylon oleare Lesne, 1932

Distribution: Northern India

Sinoxylon pachyodon Lesne, 1906

Distribution: Burma, Thailand

Sinoxylon parviclava Lesne, 1918

Distribution: Burma, Vietnam, Indonesia (Celebes)

Sinoxylon perforans (Schrank, 1789)

Distribution: Southern Europe, Caucasus, Turkey, Middle East

Sinoxylon philippinense Lesne, 1938

Distribution: Philippines

Sinoxylon pubens Lesne, 1906

Distribution: Southern India

Sinoxylon pugnax Lesne, 1904

Distribution: India, Pakistan, Iran

Sinoxylon pygmaeum Lesne, 1897

Distribution: India, Burma, Vietnam

Sinoxylon rejectum (Hope, 1845)

Distribution: China

Sinoxylon ruficorne Fahraeus, 1871

Distribution: Africa South of Sahara, USA (introduced)

Sinoxylon rufobasale Fairmaire, 1888

Distribution: South Africa

Sinoxylon rugicauda Lesne, 1929

Distribution: Malay Peninsula

Sinoxylon senegalense Karsch, 1881

Distribution: Sahara Region, West and East Africa, Europe (introduced)

Sinoxylon succisum Lesne, 1895

Distribution: Morocco, Tunisia, West Africa

Sinoxylon sudanicum Lesne, 1895

Distribution: Sudan, Senegal, Egypt, Yemen, India, Europe (Germany) (introduced)

Sinoxylon tignarium Lesne, 1902

Distribution: India (Sikkim, Assam), South-West, China, Vietnam

Sinoxylon transvaalense Lesne, 1895

Distribution: Africa South of Sahara

Sinoxylon unidentatum (Fabricius, 1801)

Distribution: Cosmopolitan

Sinoxylon verrugerum Lesne 1906

Distribution: Togo

Sinoxylon villosum Lesne, 1895

Distribution: South Africa

Genus *Xyloperthodes* Lesne, 1906

Xyloperthodes abruptus (Lesne, 1906)

Distribution: Guinea Bissau

Xyloperthodes calvula Lesne, 1906

Distribution: East and South Africa, Zanzibar

Xyloperthodes castaneipennis (Fahraeus, 1871)

Distribution: South-East Africa

Xyloperthodes collarti Lesne, 1935

Distribution: Central Africa

Xyloperthodes discedens Lesne, 1906

Distribution: West Africa

Xyloperthodes discicollis (Fairmaire, 1893)

Distribution: Abyssinia, Eritrea

Xyloperthodes evops Lesne, 1906

Distribution: South Africa

Xyloperthodes granulatus Lesne 1906

Distribution: Madagascar

Xyloperthodes houssiaui Vrydagh, 1955

Distribution: Zaire

Xyloperthodes hova Lesne, 1906

Distribution: Madagascar

Xyloperthodes incertus Lesne, 1906

Distribution: East and South Africa

Xyloperthodes nasifer Lesne, 1906

Distribution: Madagascar

Xyloperthodes nitidipennis (Murray, 1867)

Distribution: Africa South of Sahara, Europe (Great Britain, Germany) (introduced)

Xyloperthodes orthogonius Lesne, 1906

Distribution: Ivory Coast

Xyloperthodes pollicifer Vrydagh, 1955

Distribution: Zaire

Xyloperthodes schedli Vrydagh, 1959

Distribution: Zaire

Tribe *Xyloperthini* Lesne, 1921

Genus *Amintinus* Borowski & Wegrzynowicz, 2007

Amintinus aethiopicus Lesne, 1938

Distribution: Abyssinia

Amintinus gardneri Vrydagh, 1959
Distribution: Uganda

Amintinus lootensi Damoiseau, 1968
Distribution: Congo

Amintinus minutissimus Damoiseau, 1968
Distribution: Congo

Amintinus ruwenzorius Vrydagh, 1955
Distribution: Zaire

Amintinus sakalavus Lesne, 1939
Distribution: Madagascar

Amintinus subtilis Lesne, 1939
Distribution: East Africa

Amintinus tenuis Lesne, 1938
Distribution: Uganda, Kenya, Congo

Genus *Calonistes* Lesne, 1936

Calonistes antennalis Lesne, 1936
Distribution: Malaysia

Genus *Calophagus* Lesne, 1902

Calophagus pekinensis Lesne, 1902
Distribution: China

Genus *Ctenobstrychus* Reichardt, 1962

Ctenobstrychus alverneri Reichardt, 1962
Distribution: Brazil

Genus *Dendrobiella* Casey, 1898

Dendrobiella aspera (LeConte, 1858)
Distribution: USA, Mexico, Guatemala

Dendrobiella isthmicola Lesne, 1933
Distribution: Greater Antilles, Mexico

Dendrobiella leechi Vrydagh, 1960
Distribution: USA. Mexico, Guatemala

Dendrobiella sericans (LeConte, 1858)
Distribution: USA. Mexico, Guatemala

Dendrobiella sericea (Mulsant et Wachanru, 1852)
Distribution: Cuba, Santo Domingo, Jamaica, Central America, Colombia

Genus *Enneadesmus* Mulsant, 1851

Enneadesmus auricomus (Reitter, 1898)
Distribution: Iran, Syria, Turkmenistan, Uzbekistan

Enneadesmus bigranulum Lesne, 1901
Distribution: Madagascar

Enneadesmus crassispina Lesne, 1936
Distribution: East and South-West Africa

Enneadesmus decorsei Lesne, 1901
Distribution: Madagascar

Enneadesmus evacanthus Lesne, 1901
Distribution: East Africa

Enneadesmus forficula (Fairmaire, 1883)
Distribution: Africa, Arabian Peninsula, Iran, Europe (Crete)

Enneadesmus mariae Lesne, 1935
Distribution: South-East Africa, Congo

Enneadesmus masculinus Lesne, 1936
Distribution: Namibia

Enneadesmus nigrutilus Lesne, 1937
Distribution: East Africa

Enneadesmus obtusidentatus Lesne, 1899
Distribution: Arabian Peninsula, Egypt, Iraq, Iran, Eritrea, Ethiopia, Europe (Germany)
(introduced)

Enneadesmus scopini Fursov, 1936
Distribution: Uzbekistan

Enneadesmus sculptifrons Lesne, 1905
Distribution: South Africa

Enneadesmus trispinosus (Olivier, 1795)

Distribution: South-West Europe, North Africa, Canary Islands, Iraq

Genus ***Mesoxylion*** Vrydagh, 1955

Mesoxylion collaris (Erichson, 1842)

Distribution: East and South Australia, Tasmania

Mesoxylion cylindricus (MacLeay, 1873)

Distribution: East and South Australia, Tasmania, New Zealand

Mesoxylion perarmatus (Lesne, 1901)

Distribution: East Australia

Genus ***Octodesmus*** Lesne, 1901

Octodesmus episternalis Lesne, 1901

Distribution: Northern India, Burma, USA (introduced)

Octodesmus kamoli Chujo, 1964

Distribution: Thailand

Octodesmus minutissimus Lesne, 1932

Distribution: India

Octodesmus parvulus (Lesne, 1897)

Distribution: Southern India, Europe (Great Britain) (introduced)

Genus ***Paraxylion*** Lesne, 1941

Paraxylion bifer (Lesne 1932)

Distribution: India, South-East Asia

Genus ***Paraxylogenes*** Damoiseau, 1968

Paraxylogenes pistaciae Damoiseau, 1968

Distribution: Iran, Iraq, Pakistan

Genus ***Plioxylion*** Vrydagh, 1955

Plioxylion plurispinis (Lesne, 1895)

Distribution: East and South Africa

Genus *Psicula* Lesne, 1941

Psicula heterogama Lesne, 1941

Distribution: India (Sikkim)

Genus *Scobicia* Lesne, 1901

Scobicia arizonica Lesne, 1907

Distribution: USA (Arizona, Texas)

Scobicia barbata (Wollaston, 1860)

Distribution: Madeira, Azores, USA (introduced)

Scobicia barbifrons (Wollaston 1864)

Distribution: Canary Islands

Scobicia bidentata (Horn, 1878)

Distribution: USA (District of Columbia, Georgia, Illinois, Indiana, Michigan, Nebraska, New Jersey, New York, Virginia, Kansas, Maryland, Texas)

Scobicia chevrieri Villa et Villa, 1835

Distribution: South Europe, North Africa, Middle East, USA (introduced)

Scobicia declivis (LeConte, 1859)

Distribution: USA [California, Oregon, Washington, Hawaii (introduced)]

Scobicia ficicola (Wollaston, 1865)

Distribution: Canary Islands

Scobicia lesnei Fisher, 1950

Distribution: USA (Texas)

Scobicia monticola Fisher, 1950

Distribution: USA (Arizona)

Scobicia pustulata (Fabricius, 1801)

Distribution: South Europe North Africa, Middle East

Scobicia suturalis (Horn, 1878)

Distribution: USA (California)

Genus *Sifidius* Borowski and Wegrzynowicz, 2007

Sifidius confusus Lesne, 1939

Distribution: Guatemala

Sifidius dampfi Lesne, 1939

Distribution: Mexico

Genus *Tetrapriocera* Horn, 1878

Tetrapriocera caprina Lesne, 1931

Distribution: Argentina

Tetrapriocera defracta Lesne, 1901

Distribution: Brazil, Argentina, Paraguay

Tetrapriocera longicornis (Olivier, 1795)

Distribution: USA (Florida), Cuba, Haiti, Santo Domingo, Puerto Rico, Saint Thomas, Grenada, Mexico, Colombia, Venezuela, Ecuador (Galapagos Islands), Peru, Brazil, Europe (Germany) (introduced)

Tetrapriocera oceanina Lesne, 1901

Distribution: Marquises Islands

Genus *Xylion* Lesne, 1901

Xylion adustus (Fahraeus, 1871)

Distribution: Africa South of Sahara, Madagascar, Comoros, Europe (Great Britain) (introduced)

Xylion falcifer Lesne, 1901

Distribution: East and South Africa

Xylion inflaticauda Lesne, 1901

Distribution: West and Central Africa

Xylion laceratus Lesne, 1901

Distribution: East and South Africa

Xylion medius Lesne, 1923

Distribution: West Africa

Xylion securifer Lesne, 1901

Distribution: West Africa, USA (introduced)

Xylion senegambianus Lesne, 1923

Distribution: West Africa

Genus *Xylionopsis* Lesne, 1937

Xylionopsis browni Vrydagh, 1959

Distribution: Uganda

Xylionopsis matruelis Damoiseau, 1968

Distribution: Congo

Xylionopsis urkerewana Lesne, 1937

Distribution: East Africa

Genus *Xylionulus* Lesne, 1901

Xylionulus epigrus Lesne, 1906

Distribution: South Africa

Xylionulus maynei Basilewsky, 1954

Distribution: West Africa

Xylionulus pusillus (Fahraeus, 1871)

Distribution: South Africa, Madagascar

Xylionulus transvena (Lesne, 1900)

Distribution: Africa South of Sahara, Brazil (introduced)

Genus *Xylobiops* Casey, 1898

Xylobiops basilaris (Say, 1824)

Distribution: Canada, USA, Europe (Great Britain, Germany) (introduced)

Xylobiops concisus Lesne, 1901

Distribution: Venezuela, Colombia

Xylobiops parilis Lesne, 1901

Distribution: USA (South-West region), Mexico, Costa Rica, Jamaica

Xylobiops sextuberculatus (LeConte, 1858)

Distribution: USA (California, Arizona), Mexico

Xylobiops texanus (Horn, 1878)

Distribution: USA (South and East Regions), Mexico, Jamaica

Genus *Xyloblaptus* Lesne, 1901

Xyloblaptus mexicanus Lesne, 1939

Distribution: Mexico

Xyloblaptus prosopidis Fisher 1950

Distribution: USA (California)

Xyloblaptus quadrispinosus (LeConte, 1866)

Distribution: USA (Arizona, California, New Mexico, Texas)

Genus *Xylobosca* Lesne, 1901

Xylobosca bispinosa (MacLeay, 1873)

Distribution: Australia

Xylobosca canina (Blackburn, 1893)

Distribution: Australia, Tasmania

Xylobosca capitosa Lesne, 1906

Distribution: West Australia

Xylobosca cuspidata Lesne, 1906

Distribution: Australia

Xylobosca decisa Lesne, 1906

Distribution: Australia

Xylobosca gemina Lesne 1901

Distribution: East Australia

Xylobosca mystica (Blackburn, 1890)

Distribution: South Australia

Xylobosca nevoissi Vrydagh, 1957

Distribution: Australia

Xylobosca spinifrons Lesne, 1906

Distribution: Australia

Xylobosca vicaria Lesne, 1906

Distribution: Australia

Xylobosca vidua (Blackburn, 1890)

Distribution: Australia

Genus *Xylocis* Lesne, 1901

Xylocis tortilicornis Lesne, 1901

Distribution: India, Sri Lanka

Genus *Xylodectes* Lesne, 1901

Xylodectes ornatus (Lesne, 1897)

Distribution: India, Burma, Laos, Vietnam, Philippines, Indonesia (Sumatra, Borneo)

Xylodectes venustus Lesne, 1901

Distribution: East Australia

Genus *Xylodeleis* Lesne, 1901

Xylodeleis obsipa (Germar, 1848)

Distribution: Australia, Tasmania, New Zealand, Sri Lanka

Genus *Xylodrypta* Lesne 1901

Xylodrypta bostrychoides Lesne, 1901

Distribution: India

Genus *Xylogenes* Lesne, 1901

Xylogenes dilatatus (Reitter, 1889)

Distribution: Azerbaijan, Iran, Iraq, Middle East, Turkmenistan

Xylogenes granulicauda Lesne, 1941

Distribution: West Australia

Xylogenes hirticollis (Blackburn, 1897)

Distribution: North-western and South Australia

Xylogenes mesopotamicus Lesne, 1937

Distribution: Syria, Iraq, Armenia

Xylogenes semenovi Lesne, 1904

Distribution: Central Asia

Xylogenes indicola Lesne, 1936

Distribution: Pakistan

Genus *Xylomeira* Lesne, 1901

Xylomeira tridens (Fabricius, 1792)

Distribution: USA (Texas, Florida), Mexico, Greater Antilles (Cuba, Jamaica, Puerto Rico),
Lesser Antilles (Antigua, Guadeloupe, Saint Lucia, Grenada)

Genus *Xylopertha* Guerin-Meneville, 1845

Xylopertha dunensis Rai et Chatterjee, 1964

Distribution: Northern India

Xylopertha praeusta (Germar, 1817)

Distribution: South Europe, North Africa)

Xylopertha reflexicauda (Lesne, 1937)

Distribution: Iran, Pakistan

Xylopertha retusa (Olivier, 1790)

Distribution: Central and South Europe, North Africa

Genus *Xyloperthella* Fisher, 1950

Xyloperthella crinitarsis (Imhoff, 1843)

Distribution: West Africa, San Thome, USA (introduced), Europe (introduced)

Xyloperthella guineensis Roberts, 1967

Distribution: Nigeria

Xyloperthella picea (Olivier, 1790)

Distribution: South Europe, Arabian Peninsula, Africa, Madagascar, South America

Xyloperthella scutula (Lesne, 1901)

Distribution: West Africa, Abyssinia

Genus *Xylophorus* Lesne, 1906

Xylophorus abnormis Lesne, 1906

Distribution: Sri Lanka

Xylophorus ceylonicus Lesne, 1941

Distribution: Sri Lanka

Genus *Xyloprista* Lesne, 1901

Xyloprista arcellata (Lesne, 1901)

Distribution: Brazil

Xyloprista fisheri Rai, 1978

Distribution: India

Xyloprista hexacantha (Fairmaire, 1892)

Distribution: Brazil, Argentina, Paraguay, Uruguay, Colombia, USA (introduced)

Xyloprista praemorsa (Erichson, 1847)

Distribution: Venezuela, Colombia, Peru, Bolivia, Brazil, Paraguay

Genus *Xylopsocus* Lesne 1901

Xylopsocus acutespinosus Lesne, 1906

Distribution: Burma

Xylopsocus bicuspis Lesne 1901

Distribution: Taiwan, Japan

Xylopsocus burnsi Vrydagh, 1958

Distribution: Australia

Xylopsocus capucinus (Fabricius, 1781)

Distribution: Madagascar, Comoros, Reunion, Mauritius, India, Sri Lanka, Burma, Vietnam, Cambodia, Indonesia, New guinea, New Caledonia, Oceania, Africa (introduced), South America (introduced), USA (introduced)

Xylopsocus castanoptera (Fairmaire, 1850)

Distribution: East Africa, Madagascar, Mauritius, Comoros, Bangladesh, Vietnam, Malaysia (Sarawak), New Guinea, Australia, Tahiti, Hawaii, Solomon Islands, USA (introduced)

Xylopsocus distinctus Rai, 1967

Distribution: India (Uttar Pradesh)

Xylopsocus ebeninocollis Lesne, 1901

Distribution: New Guinea

Xylopsocus edentatus (Montrouzier, 1861)

Distribution: New Caledonia (Lifou)

Xylopsocus ensifer Lesne 1906

Distribution: Burma

Xylopsocus galloisi Lesne, 1937

Distribution: Japan

Xylopsocus gibbicollis (MacLeay, 1873)

Distribution: New Guinea, Australia, Tasmania, New Zealand

Xylopsocus indianus Vrydagh, 1959

Distribution: India

Xylopsocus intermedius Damoiseau in Damoiseau et Coulon, 1993

Distribution: Vietnam

Xylopsocus philippinensis Vrydagh, 1955

Distribution: Philippines

Xylopsocus radula Lesne, 1901

Distribution: Burma, Indonesia (Sumatra)

Xylopsocus ritsemai Lesne, 1906

Distribution: Indonesia (Java)

Xylopsocus rubidus Lesne, 1901

Distribution: West Australia

Xylopsocus sellatus (Fahraeus, 1871)

Distribution: East Africa, Madagascar

Genus *Xylothrips* Lesne, 1901

Xylothrips cathaicus Reichardt, 1966

Distribution: China

Xylothrips flavipes (Illiger, 1801)

Distribution: Madagascar, Comoros, Seychelles, Reunion, Mauritius, Arabian Peninsula, Yemen (Socotra), Natal, Israel, South-East Asia, Indonesia, Philippines, Europe (introduced), USA (introduced)

Xylothrips geoffroyi (Montrouzier, 1861)

Distribution: New Caledonia

Xylothrips religiosus (Boisduval, 1835)

Distribution: New Guinea, New Caledonia, Fiji, Tahiti, Australia, Hawaii, USA (introduced), Africa (introduced), Europe (introduced)

Genus *Xylotillus* Lesne, 1901

Xylotillus lindi (Blackburn, 1890)

Distribution: East and South Australia

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